

Modular programme for Education and Training

YOUTH SPORT COACH

M#6 Plan, Reflect and Learn

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For further information on the EduPASS Project please follow the link:

Website: <https://edupass-project.eu/>

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Six Core Modules of EduPASS Modular Programme for Education and Training for Youth Sport Coach

The following are the proposed six core modules for Youth Sport Coaches education and training programmes that were developed as part of the EduPASS Erasmus+ Project. The core modules should be seen as a flexible reference point which require contextual adaptation. Those individuals and/or organisations using the six core modules to develop learning opportunities for Youth Sport Coaches should use the knowledge of their specific context to customise the modules to fit their needs, resources and objectives.

Each of the six EduPASS core modules proposed for YSC education and training programmes was developed building on the knowledge and insights, which can be found in the [European Coaching Children Curriculum \(ECCC\)](#). The ECCC, in turn, is built around the Primary Functions of the Coach as described in the European Sport Coaching Framework (2017) ([CoachLearn | European Sport Coaching Framework](#)) and the [International Sport Coaching Framework \(2013\)](#).

The respective module number and order in which the modules are presented in the table below do not indicate that modules must be introduced in this specific order, when implementing a Youth Sport Coach education and training programme. Rather the numbers simply serve as distinct denominators to help identify specific modules in the overall context of the EduPASS YSC education and training programme.

Core Module Overview

No	Module Title	Description
1	Daily Physical Activity and Sport & Motor Skills Assessment	<p>Daily physical activity, Movement, Play, and Sports (PAMPS) has many benefits for children – physically, psychologically, emotionally and cognitively. In this context, the development of physical literacy of each child is essential.</p> <p>Awareness of trends in children’s participation levels, physical activity guidelines, the needs and wants of children and how to engage with children in age-appropriate ways, will assist the coach.</p> <p>Knowledge on the growth and development of children in all aspects (socially, physically, emotionally and cognitively) is essential.</p> <p>This should be underpinned by the coach’s personal values and beliefs about the role of PAMPS for children and young people and</p>

		<p>about what constitutes ‘good practice’ (their coaching philosophy).</p> <p>To support individual children and to develop programmes based on their needs, the ability to assess motor skills will guide this work.</p>
2	Principles of Coaching Children	<p>The principles of good coaching practice with children should be used by the Youth Sport Coach (YSC). These form the basis for the 10 principles of the ICOACHKIDS Pledge:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Principle 1 — Be child-centred • Principle 2 — Be holistic • Principle 3 — Be inclusive • Principle 4 — Make it fun and safe • Principle 5 — Prioritise the love for sport over learning sport • Principle 6 — Focus on foundational skills • Principle 7 — Engage parents positively • Principle 8 — Plan progressive programmes • Principle 9 — Use difference methods to enhance learning • Principle 10 — Use competition in a developmental way <p>The YSC develops a programme based on their needs and the stage of development of children, based on the principles of coaching children.</p> <p>The YSC seeks to optimise the environment in which the programme occurs. The ability to navigate this can be guided by the Youth Sport Compass. The compass has 4 pillars – Developmental, Motivational, Caring and Social Safety – which can guide the YSC.</p> <p>The organisational and social context of the programme, including the participants (children/parents/club) should be taken into account.</p>
3	Inclusive Coaching / Safeguarding	<p>The Youth Sport Coach builds positive and effective relationships and works with a group of participants (children, club, school, parents, federation and other levels) and takes responsibility for the realisation of the common and individual objectives, and to achieve the programme and club goals. Hearing ‘the Voice’ of each child is an important component of this.</p> <p>Safeguarding and child protection must underpin the establishment of a safe environment for children in sport.</p>
4	Fundamental Movement	<p>Children should develop foundational motor skills to underpin their love of being active and to have the competence to engage in a range of activities. The development of fundamental</p>

	Skills and Play	<p>movement (balance, agility, coordination, speed) and motor skills (run, move, jump, land, throw, catch, kick, etc) is essential, and is supported by contexts that engage children in fundamental play activities.</p>
5	Hands-on Coaching	<p>The Youth Sport Coach needs to develop their personal coaching skills and coaching tools. These include - introducing activities, demonstration, set-up and stand back, questioning and listening, feedback and reflection.</p> <p>Based on the principles of coaching children, inclusive coaching, and development of fundamental motor skills, the YSC needs to plan and organise suitable and challenging practices and attendance at events, using effective pedagogy and methodology, to promote the learning and improvement of children.</p> <p>The development of personal coaching skills and the planning of practices/events need to be practiced both with peers and in experiential learning situations with children. Thus, the aim of this module is to help craft safe learning experiences where “coaches learn how to coach by coaching”. Those hands-on coaching experiences enable coach learners to prepare coaching, engage in, and have an opportunity to receive feedback and engage in self-reflection about their coaching practice.</p>
6	Plan, Reflect and Learn	<p>The environment, which Youth Sport Coaches contribute to, can be welcoming and inclusive to all children. Individual coaches can provide this in their personal coaching and can also contribute to a club / school having child-centred values and policies. The Youth Sport Coach will examine their personal coaching philosophy and a means to support a club / school to adopt child-centred values and policies.</p> <p>Reflection on practice has been identified as a key means of learning and ongoing development for coaches. This can be supported by engaging with others and to a club / school being a learning environment for coaches (as well as children). Reflection is a learned skill and the Youth Sport Coach will reflect on their practice individually, with co-coaches and with a mentor.</p>

Youth Sport Coach – Programme Outcomes

The action-oriented outcomes and results for coaches for the complete module programme for Education and Training are presented below. The outcomes have been adapted from the [European Sport Coaching Framework](#) (Human Kinetics, 2017).

	The Youth Sport Coach in training will have taken the first steps towards being able to:
Coaching Vision and Strategy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Develop a suitable vision for the programme relevant to the participants (and in line with institutional priorities) • Make effective and informed decisions relating to the planning, implementation, monitoring and evaluation of mid- to long-term programmes (of practice and competition) based on (institutional and) participant needs • Encourage adopting sustainable, life-long engagement in PAMPS / Daily PA
Shape the Environment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Know how to identify, reflect on and challenge prevailing beliefs, values and assumptions within the coaching environment to establish a suitable culture for PAMPS • Know how to create an environment where all children feel safe and included • Know about and be able to identify potential dangers for children in sport • Contribute to crafting and upholding a coaching environment / club / school that has child-centred values and policies • Build a community of practice and contribute to the on-going learning of other coaches and that where they coach is a learning environment for coaches.
Building Positive Relationships	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Know how to establish and maintain an ethical, effective, inclusive and empathetic relationship with children and other stakeholders (e.g., parents) • Understand how to appreciate physical, mental and cultural diversity in children and adapt PAMPS practice accordingly
Coaching Practice	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Know how to conduct (comprehensive) needs analyses (assessments) for individual children (and/or teams) in order to design and deliver tailored coaching programmes, taking into account children needs and capabilities (in the context of wider programmes, curricula, policies and targets) • Understand how to select, design and justify appropriate pedagogy, practice and communication methods to facilitate the short, medium and long-term learning needs of children • Understand the core elements of multi skills or of their chosen sport(s) at the key stages of child development • Know how to deliver a series of coaching sessions in the context of medium term and long term planned programmes of practice and competition using a

	wide range of appropriate learning modes for children and coaching behaviours
Decision Making	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Understand how to conduct an informed analysis of own performance and of the performance of children towards ensuring continuous progress and improvement • Understand how to make good in-action and post-action decisions to increase the chances of reaching short-, mid- and long-term objectives • Apply knowledge of fundamentals of movement, fundamental movement skills and fundamental game skills to create practices that lead to short-term and long-term learning, including play • Apply knowledge of motor skill development for children and youth, including the stages/phases of skill development and the impact of growth and maturation
Coaching Review and Reflection	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Know how to conduct an insightful analysis of coaching practice to make informed judgements relating to the efficacy of the learning environment established • Reflect on their personal coaching knowledge, skills, attitudes, values, and practice, with the aim of continuously improving • Continuously build and engage with a network of coaches / coach developers to keep reviewing and building personal best-practices in coaching children, seeking supervised hands-on coaching contexts

Module Structure

Core Module	Plan, Reflect and Learn
Module Number	6
Core Module Aim	<p>The aim of the core module is to achieve that Youth Sport Coaches:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Plan that their coaching environment / club / school has child-centred values and policies. Plan that their own coaching is child-centred, with a clear child-centred coaching philosophy. Reflect on their personal coaching knowledge, skills, attitudes, values, and practice, with the aim of continuously improving. Learn through their own reflection and from engagement with the children they coach, their parents, co-coaches, mentors and communities of practice. Contribute to the on-going learning of other coaches and that where they coach is a learning environment for coaches.
Module Description	<p>The environment, which Youth Sport Coaches contribute to, can be welcoming and inclusive to all children. Individual coaches can provide this in their personal coaching and can also contribute to a club / school having child-centred values and policies. The Youth Sport Coach will examine their personal coaching philosophy and a means to support a club / school to adopt child-centred values and policies.</p> <p>Reflection on practice has been identified as a key means of learning and ongoing development for coaches. This can be supported by engaging with others and to a club / school being a learning environment for coaches (as well as children). Reflection is a learned skill and the Youth Sport Coach will reflect on their practice individually, with co-coaches and with a mentor.</p>
Module Duration	At least 30 hours (20 hrs lectures/workshops, 10 hrs self-directed learning)
Facilities and Equipment	Seminar room and gym
Methodology	Class based and field-based presentations, during which the coach will be involved in planning (for club / personal coaching philosophy / practical coaching); and after coaching practice, reflection on their personal coaching skills and knowledge, individually, as a group of co-coaches and with a mentor.
Coaching Materials	Logbook / reflection book
Suggested Readings	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> MOOC 1, Chapter 1, Section 2: Children Sport – Reality Check - Chapter-1-The-Role-of-the-Childrens-Sport-Coach-Study-Guide.pdf (assets-servd.host) and associated video - iCK Course#1-Ch1-S2-Children's Sport: A Reality Check (youtube.com) MOOC 1, Chapter 2: Chapter-2-What-is-a-coaching-philosophy-and-why-it-is-beneficial-to-be-clear-about-yours-Study-Guide.pdf (assets-

	<p>servd.host) and associated videos - iCK Course#1-Ch2-Intro-What is a Coaching Philosophy and Why it is Beneficial... (youtube.com)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • MOOC 1, Chapter 3: Creating A vision and Strategy for Your Club - Chapter-3-How-to-create-a-suitable-vision-for-your-team-or-your-club-Study-Guide.pdf (assets-servd.host) and associated video - iCK Course#1-Ch3-Intro-Creating a Vision and Strategy for Your Team or Club (youtube.com) • MOOC 3, Chapter 1: Planning for Success - Chapter-1-Planning-for-Success-Study-Guide.pdf (assets-servd.host) and associated videos, starting with iCK Course#3 Introduction - Coaching on the Ground: Planning, Doing and Reviewing (youtube.com) • MOOC 3, Chapter 4: Reflective Tools for Coaches - Chapter-4-Reflective-Tools-for-Coaches-Study-Guide.pdf (assets-servd.host) and associated videos, starting with iCK Course #3 Ch4 Intro - The Lifelong Learning Coach - YouTube 				
Evaluation	EduPASS Evaluation Tool for Youth Sport Coach Programmes				
Module structure <i>(each module requires AT LEAST 2 courses)</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Course 6.1: Child-Centred Planning for Clubs / Schools and alignment of Personal Coaching Philosophy <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ 5 h Lecture Teaching Units ○ 5 h Workshop/Practical Teaching Units ○ 5 h Self-Directed Working hours • Course 6.2: Reflection and Learning <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ 5 h Lecture Teaching Units ○ 5 h Workshop/Practical Teaching Units ○ 5 h Self-Directed Working hours 				
Learning outcomes <i>for Youth Sport Coaches</i>	<p>The module will enable the Youth Sport Coach in training to build the following competencies (knowledge, skills, attitudes, values) which serve as a foundation when engaging with the children they coach:</p> <table border="1" data-bbox="470 1328 1412 2069"> <tr> <td data-bbox="470 1328 965 1668"> <p>Knowledge:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • awareness about their interests & preferences • regarding basic motor development processes • fundamentals of social interaction • benefits of play & exploration • activities in PAMPS </td> <td data-bbox="965 1328 1412 1668"> <p>Skills:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fun and enjoyment • Communication skills • Cooperation skills • Motivation skills • Active Listening skills </td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="470 1668 965 2069"> <p>Attitudes: <i>Children will have engaged in activities that foster development of the following attitudes when engaging in PAMPS activities with other children:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Respecting other children’s needs and interests • Enthusiasm • Creativity </td> <td data-bbox="965 1668 1412 2069"> <p>Values: <i>Children will have engaged in activities that foster development of the following values when engaging in PAMPS activities with other children:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Respect • Fair play • Cooperation </td> </tr> </table>	<p>Knowledge:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • awareness about their interests & preferences • regarding basic motor development processes • fundamentals of social interaction • benefits of play & exploration • activities in PAMPS 	<p>Skills:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fun and enjoyment • Communication skills • Cooperation skills • Motivation skills • Active Listening skills 	<p>Attitudes: <i>Children will have engaged in activities that foster development of the following attitudes when engaging in PAMPS activities with other children:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Respecting other children’s needs and interests • Enthusiasm • Creativity 	<p>Values: <i>Children will have engaged in activities that foster development of the following values when engaging in PAMPS activities with other children:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Respect • Fair play • Cooperation
<p>Knowledge:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • awareness about their interests & preferences • regarding basic motor development processes • fundamentals of social interaction • benefits of play & exploration • activities in PAMPS 	<p>Skills:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fun and enjoyment • Communication skills • Cooperation skills • Motivation skills • Active Listening skills 				
<p>Attitudes: <i>Children will have engaged in activities that foster development of the following attitudes when engaging in PAMPS activities with other children:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Respecting other children’s needs and interests • Enthusiasm • Creativity 	<p>Values: <i>Children will have engaged in activities that foster development of the following values when engaging in PAMPS activities with other children:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Respect • Fair play • Cooperation 				

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cooperation • Fun and enjoyment • Empathy • Patience 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Empathy • Inclusion • Honesty
Learning outcomes <i>for children/learners</i>	The module will enable the Youth Sport Coach in training to support the children they coach to develop the following competencies (knowledge, skills, attitudes, values):	
	Knowledge: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • awareness about their interests & preferences • regarding basic motor development processes • fundamentals of social interaction 	Skills: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fun and enjoyment • Inclusive Communication skills • Cooperation skills • Motivation skills • Active Listening skills
	Attitudes: <i>Children will have engaged in activities that foster development of the following attitudes when engaging in PAMPS activities with other children:</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Respecting other children’s needs and interests • Enthusiasm • Creativity • Cooperation • Open-mindedness • Fun and enjoyment • Empathy • Patience 	Values: <i>Children will have engaged in activities that foster development of the following values when engaging in PAMPS activities with other children:</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Respect • Fair play • Cooperation • Empathy • Inclusion • Honesty • Teamwork • Friendship • Positive Relationships
Connection to other Core Module	Module 6 connects to all other Modules 1-5. Throughout all these modules we deem it essential for instructors and learners to implement a “Plan, Reflect, Learn” approach. To highlight this critical skill and provide specific ideas how to engage with and improve in it, we have drafted these module and course descriptions for Module 6.	

Course Structure

Course Title	Child-Centred Planning for Clubs / Schools and alignment of Personal Coaching Philosophy		
Course Number	6.1		
Course Description / Main Objective	<p>The Youth Sport Coach in training will be able to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Plan that their coaching environment / club / school has child-centred values and policies. Plan that their own coaching is child-centred, with a clear child-centred coaching philosophy. 		
Course Structure <i>(each module requires AT LEAST 2 Teaching Units)</i>	L	5 h	Teaching Unit 1: The Role of the Children’s Coach in the Club
	W / PE	5 h	Teaching Unit 2: Alignment of coaching philosophy and coaching behaviours
	SDL	5 h	Teaching Unit 3: Complete the tasks in the ICOACHKIDS MOOCs
Course Content <i>(examples of specific Course Content based on EduPASS LTT workshops are shared as separate slide decks)</i>	TU 1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The Coach Decision Making Model (ESCF, 2017 - CoachLearn European Sport Coaching Framework) Personal Coaching Philosophy, its development and growth A child-centred vision and strategy for a club / school Planning, doing and reviewing on the ground 	
	TU 2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The clubs/ schools policy and values and your personal coaching philosophy in practice(practice of coaching and review of coaching behaviours) – are they aligned? 	
	TU 3	<p>Complete the activities in:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> MOOC 1, Chapter 1, Section 2: Children Sport – Reality Check - Chapter-1-The-Role-of-the-Childrens-Sport-Coach-Study-Guide.pdf (assets-servd.host) MOOC 1, Chapter 2: Chapter-2-What-is-a-coaching-philosophy-and-why-it-is-beneficial-to-be-clear-about-yours-Study-Guide.pdf (assets-servd.host) MOOC 1, Chapter 3: Creating A vision and Strategy for Your Club - Chapter-3-How-to-create-a-suitable-vision-for-your-team-or-your-club-Study-Guide.pdf (assets-servd.host) 	

Course Title	Reflection and Learning		
Course Number	6.2		
Course Description / Main Objective	<p>The Youth Sport Coach in training will be able to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reflect on their personal coaching knowledge, skills and practice, with the aim of continuously improving. • Learn through their own reflection and from engagement with the children they coach, their parents, co-coaches, mentors and communities of practice. • Contribute to the on-going learning of other coaches and that where they coach is a learning environment for coaches. 		
Course Structure <i>(each module requires AT LEAST 2 Teaching Units)</i>	L	5 h	Teaching Unit 1: Reflection – aim, scope and how to do it
	W / PE	5 h	Teaching Unit 2: Practice of Reflection Skills – individually, in a group and with a mentor
	SD	5 h	Teaching Unit 3: Complete a personal reflection journal and write a personal case
Course Content <i>(examples of specific Course Content based on EduPASS LTT workshops are shared as separate slide decks)</i>	TU 1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reflection during practice • Reflection on practice • Use of technology (video) • Reflection with co-coaches, with a partner and as part of a group • Learning with a mentor • Setting personal improvement goals 	
	TU 2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Practical application and development of reflection skills • Awareness of your coaching skills and behaviours; and setting of personal improvement goals • Your personal coaching philosophy in practice – practice of coaching and review of coaching behaviours – are they aligned? 	
	TU 3	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Complete a personal reflection journal, using a variety of reflection methods (individual, group, mentor, video); and write up a personal case study to include: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Review club values and policy • Create personal coaching philosophy • Evaluate coaching behaviours and alignment with philosophy • Journal reflection and change of coaching behaviour over time • Document changes and grow of your personal coaching philosophy • Continuously set personal improvement goals 	